

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATIONAL LEADERSHIP

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Annotation: *This article explores the concept of leadership with a particular focus on educational leadership and its evolving interpretations within both international and Kazakhstani contexts. Drawing on classical and contemporary theories of leadership, the paper traces how understandings of leadership have shifted from hierarchical and power-based models toward collaborative, values-driven, and change-oriented approaches.*

Special attention is given to educational leadership as a process that shapes teaching, learning, and school culture. The paper examines key dimensions of effective educational leadership, including influence, values, and vision, while acknowledging ongoing debates surrounding visionary leadership. It further analyzes the concept of leadership capacity and learning communities, highlighting the importance of collaboration, teacher leadership, and professional growth.

Key Words: *Educational leadership; leadership styles; instructional leadership; managerial leadership; leadership capacity; school leadership; teacher leadership; values and vision; educational reform; Kazakhstan.*

Leadership can be observed everywhere, in every single moment of our life and in every situation (Bass, 2008). For instance, at home, at work, at school, in a social group, in local communities, in national government and even in an international arena (p. 3). From early years there were various definitions of leadership. According to Bass (2008) in the 1930s leadership was understood as a process when people follow the leader in a specific direction. Further, in 1940s leadership was considered as an ability to persuade and direct someone without the influence of “position and power” (p. 15). In the 1950s leadership was understood like a harmony of community leader with group members. Finally, in the 1990s leadership was seen as a leader and followers together move towards changes in order to achieve common aim (p. 15). Another valuable definition of leadership was given by Dewey (1938) in his early work. He considers that leadership is possessing abilities to give others chance to build capacity, grow, understand their potential and use their skills for future development. This paper supports Dewey’s ideas and suggests that leadership is to help others to see new possibilities and to influence on positive changing.

Nowadays among leaderships educational leadership is widely spread for discussions and considered to be one of the most important directions in leadership. Educational leadership is a process of influence on learners, teachers, parents and a whole school to work towards achieving educational goals. Educational leaders are people who work on maintaining school values, following school mission and vision. Additionally, an educational leader initiates new structure and methods in order to achieve existing goal and ensures that a leader and group members work collaboratively in the best interest of the school (Duruh, 2018). According to Lambert (2003) teacher leader is engaged in everyday school challenges, feel enthusiastic about school improvement and appreciates opportunities to grow professionally, in addition this kind of environment might arouse and further develop educational leadership. However, this paper may suggest that teacher leader directs towards vision on student learning and reacts positively on constant changes in learning process. Effective definition of educational leadership can be identified by three dimensions: “Leadership as influence”, “Leadership and values”, “Leadership and vision” (Bush, 2011). Bush (2011) claims that “Leadership as influence” it is when a leader influences a group or individual to achieve a goal. This proves that “Leadership as influence” is intentional process and it is a capability to provide a chance to improve professionally and personally. The next key dimension of school leadership is “Leadership and

values” Bush (2011) says that “influence” in leadership is mostly nonaligned and in addition it does not dictate what should be followed. However, he considers that Leadership and values are immensely interrelated to each other. Bush believes that educational leadership is considered to set goals and organise actions irrespectively from personal and professional values. Day, Harris and Hadfield (2001) did a research on effective school leadership in English and Wales schools and draw a conclusion that successful leader is aware of clear communication of personal and professional values. This essay also admits that good leader sets his/her professional goals not being influenced by personal values. Furthermore, a leader who has clear vision of school achievements is tend to highly encourage his/her followers to work towards common purposes. However visionary leadership still remains arguable dimension of school leadership. For example, Hoyle and Wallace (2005) criticize huge emphasize on vision in leadership. They write that visions are centralised and in most cases are set to correspond to educational inspector’s expectations. Nevertheless, this essay may argue that vision play crucial role in educational leadership. Once students, teachers and parents understand and clearly see school vision that consequently may lead to sufficient collaborative work and academic achievements.

Recently educators were occupied with thoughts about “leadership capacity and learning communities” (Lambert, 2003). Harris and Lambert (2003) agreed that leadership capacity designs efficient learning environment where teacher leadership is valued, supported and more than welcome. They also find that collaborative activity helps to increase knowledge and skills to influence positively on future developments (p. 21). This paper agrees that leadership capacity aims to improve all school community and working collaboratively creates sufficient environment for teachers to learn through reflecting and sharing. Gunter (2004) says that the term “educational leadership” was transformed from “educational management” and this was changed from “educational administration”.

Since last decade Kazakhstan is continually experimenting educational reform in order to enter the world arena. Directing school effectively remains as one of the most critical and crucial factors in educational leadership. Nowadays schools work in composite environment. In order to follow school mission and effectively lead a school, for school administrators and teachers it is not enough to lead the classroom effectively. In this respect educators need to constantly improve their leadership skills, accept and spread changes, arrange cooperative agreements with stakeholders in school, local and state levels. It is commonly assumed that school principal is a key factor of educational leadership. In addition, Frost, Fimyar, Yakavets and Bilyalov (2014) found that in Kazakhstan school leadership mostly refers to the work of one person who is considered to be the most senior administrator in the school. Accordingly, huge attention is being paid to the training of school principals. One of the key topic in leadership training courses for Kazakhstani secondary schools principals is shifting from managerial leadership style. This style of leadership is widely spread in the school organizations across the country and used to be considered quite satisfying. However, today Kazakhstani schools admit that changes in national school curriculum is necessary and educational leaders are agents to spread these innovations. Commonly in Kazakhstan school principal is recognized to be only individual to make decisions in school level. This essay may assure that most secondary schools still have managerial and instructional leadership styles. In both of these styles “top-down approach” is maintained. Principals receive official document (GOSO) at the beginning of each school academic year which should be followed during the whole year. Instructional leadership focuses above all on the purpose and direction of leader’s influence (Bush & Glover, 2014). Bush & Glover (2014) also add that in instructional leadership there is far less attention paid on the influence process itself. Timperley (2011) in his book “Realizing the Power of Professional Learning” underlines that instructional leadership includes considerable moral purpose to promote student learning process, professional research and trusting relationship. It is important to admit that instructional leadership influences on quality of school outcomes supporting learning and learning outcomes. However, Leithwood, Jantzi and Steinbach (1999) argue that Instructional leadership mostly expects that teachers’ behaviour and their engagement in task directly affect the growth of students achievements.

This paper agrees that principals with instructional leadership believe that teacher behaviour, more involvement of teachers in paper work may lead to achievements in learning objectives and high academic results.

Managerial leadership style in Kazakhstani schools takes its root from Soviet Union period. Managerial leadership defines a principal only person who makes decisions about learners, teachers, deputy principals and all school staff. Principal is more focused on teacher behaviour rather than learning process. For example, in Kazakhstan principal is more concerned about teacher uniform and everyday schedule which is expected to be overlapped with lessons and extracurricular activities. This may be explained that a principal possesses strong belief that teachers should be responsible and all the time ready to respond and reflect in case if school final results are not satisfying. Additionally, in managerial school leadership principal sees himself as someone who gives the task, sets the functions of its execution and manages the process only. Principal in this kind of school only occasionally deals with learning process such as observing lessons, collaboratively addressing school issues, leading seminars for teaching staff, building school capacity or doing research of challenges that school has. Evidence of managerial leadership in most schools in Kazakhstan can be exemplified by “top-down approach” that these schools maintain. These additionally may rise a danger of value-free management. Schools directly depend on local educational officials who require written report on every single step that school did. This kind of system leads principals to behave more like managers rather than educational leader.

Throughout this paper it has been discussed the importance of school leadership, some styles of leadership and preferable leadership has been suggested for own workplace. Overall, it is concluded that leadership is not only organisation of others efforts but applying these efforts in achieving common wide-ranging purposes, Educational leadership requires to provide positive learning environment in schools and well-meaning school culture for all stakeholders. In addition, careful review of the literature on educational leadership revealed that there is no one model of effective leadership for schools. Every school needs to identify the most successful leadership style which suits best their school. This leadership style is expected to meet requirements of all school members, build the capacity of staff, create opportunities to solve academic issues collaboratively and the most essential to foster the generation of future leaders.

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